

CHARACTERISTICS OF SUICIDES IN FORENSIC PRACTICE

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ABSTRACT

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), every 40 seconds someone on Earth takes their own life. According to WHO statistics, suicide is the second leading cause of death among young people (aged 15–29) globally. Three thousand people commit suicide daily worldwide, and approximately one million people commit suicide annually (1.5% of all deaths)..

Introduction. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), every 40 seconds someone on Earth takes their own life. According to WHO statistics, suicide is the second leading cause of death among young people (aged 15–29) globally. Three thousand people commit suicide daily worldwide, and approximately one million people commit suicide annually (1.5% of all deaths).

Suicides occupy a significant place among fatal outcomes and negatively impact public health. Therefore, a detailed analysis of mortality, including its structure and causes, plays a crucial role in implementing various preventive measures.

Objective of the study: To determine the types of suicides by gender, sex, age, and seasonality using forensic medical records.

Materials and methods: We conducted a retrospective analysis of forensic medical examination reports from corpses conducted at the Samarkand Regional Branch of the Republican Scientific and Practical Center for Forensic Medical Examination and its district branches.

Results. A total of 182 suicide cases were examined at the Samarkand branch. The following suicide types were identified: self-hanging (166 cases, 91.2%), thermal trauma and train accidents (4 each, 2.2%), poisoning and drowning (3 each, 1.6%), and falls from height and sharp object injuries (1 each, 0.5%).

In terms of gender, there were 87 women (47.8%) and 95 men (52.2%). In terms of age, 30 cases (16.5%) involved minors aged 14 to 18, of which 18 were female (60.0%) and 12 male (40.0%), including 10 persons under 14 (33.3%); in the 19-30 year old group, there were 75 cases (41.2%), of which 47 were female (62.7%) and 28 male (37.3%); in the 31-40 year old group, there were 29 cases (15.9%), of which 10 were female (34.5%) and 19 male (65.5%); In the 41-50 year old group there were 24 cases (13.2%), including 4 females (16.7%) and 20 males (83.3%); in the 51-60 year old group there were 16 cases (8.8%), including 7 females (43.8%) and 9 males (56.2%); in the over 60 year old group there were 8 cases (4.4%), including 1 female (12.5%) and 7 males (87.5%).

The study by seasons revealed the following: in winter, there were 27 suicide cases (14.8%), including 25 self-hanging cases (92.6%); in spring, there were 43 suicide cases (23.6%), including 25 self-hanging cases (58.1%); in summer, there were 67 suicide cases (36.8%), including 63 self-hanging cases (92.6%); in autumn, there were 45 suicide cases (24.7%), including 40 self-hanging cases (88.9%). The study by days of the week revealed the following picture: 27 cases (14.8%) on Monday, 22 (12.1%) on Tuesday, 27 (14.8%) on Wednesday, 24 (13.2%) on Thursday, 28 (15.4%) on Friday, 26 (14.3%) on Saturday, and 28 (15.4%) on Sunday.

Conclusion. According to forensic medical data, mechanical asphyxia, in the form of self-hanging, is significantly more prevalent in the structure of suicides among the population. Males are more likely to die from this type of suicide than females, but in the 18- to 30-year-old age group, females are significantly more likely to die from this type of suicide. Overall, age-related suicides are predominantly observed among individuals of working age. The observations among minors are alarming. A seasonal increase in the number of suicides has been observed during the summer months, while a slight increase in the number of suicides is observed towards the end of the week. This indicates the need for preventive measures in this area

